

Studies in Spiro Heterocycles. Part-III* : Synthesis of Fluorine Containing Spiro[3H-Indole-3,2'-Thiazolidine]-2,4'(1H)-Diones as Antifertility Agents

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A number of new fluorine containing spiro [3H-indole-3,2'-thiazolidine]-2,4'(1H)-diones have been synthesised by the condensation of fluorine containing indole-2,3-diones with appropriate anilines and mercapto acetic acid. Some of the compounds were screened for antifertility activity and one of these, 6-fluoro-3'-(4-fluorophenyl) spiro [3H-indole-3,2'-thiazolidine]-2,4'(1H)-dione, has shown antiimplantation activity in rats at a dose of 30 mg/kg.

THE biological activities of indole derivatives have been reviewed by Joshi *et al*¹. Various indole derivatives are reported to exhibit antifertility activity^{2,3}, and 1-(4-dimethylaminoethoxyphenyl)-5-methoxy-2-phenylindole is active at the dose of 2 mg/kg in rats⁴. Various sulphur containing heterocyclic systems like 2,3-diphenyl benzothio-phenes⁵, 2H-1-benzothiopyranes⁵, methanobenzo[b]-thiophenes⁶ have exhibited good antifertility activity and 2,3-dihydro-4-(4-pyridyl methylene)-1-benzothie-pin-5(4H)-one is active at the dose of 2 mg/day in rats⁷. 3-Aryl-4-oxothiazolin-2-yl-[3-2-(aryl)indolyl] hydrazones have also been prepared as possible antifertility agents⁸.

In continuation to our earlier work on biologically active indole derivatives⁹⁻¹² we have now synthesised the title compounds, by incorporating both the indole and the thiazolidine nuclei, as possible antifertility agents.

The synthesis of fluorine containing indole-2,3-diones has been earlier reported by us¹³. The synthesis of compounds IVa-j was accomplished in one step without isolating the intermediate (III). Fluorine containing indole-2,3-dione, when reacted with anilines, furnished an anil which was reacted *in situ* with mercapto acetic acid to give the corresponding spiro compound¹³. Physical characteristic and analytical data of all the compounds are listed in Table I.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer, model-577 spectrophotometer in KBr pellets and nmr on Bruker (HX 90) instrument at 90 MHz in CDCl₃ and DMSO with TMS as external reference. The

purity of all the compounds were checked by thin layer chromatography on silica gel plates.

Fluorine containing indole-2,3-diones (I) : 5-Fluoroindole-2,3-dione, 6-fluoroindole-2,3-dione and 4-trifluoromethylindole-2,3-dione were prepared by the literature method¹³.

5-Fluoro-3'-phenyl spiro[3H-indole-3,2'-thiazolidine]-2,4'(1H) dione (IVa) : A mixture of 5-fluoroindole-2,3-dione (I) (0.01 mole) and aniline (0.01 mole) was heated under reflux in toluene for 2 hr and theoretical amount of water was collected azeotropically. On cooling the mixture, mercapto acetic acid (0.011 mole) was added and refluxed again for 4 hr under the same conditions. Thereafter, the reaction mixture was allowed to cool at room temp., and the supernatant liquid decanted off. The solid obtained, on recrystallization from ethanol, afforded the pure colourless crystals, yield 80%, m.p. 265°; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{cm}^{-1}}$: 1640-1730 (>C=O), 3320 (>NH); pmr (CDCl₃) δ : 3.9-4.3 (CH₂), 7.8 (NH) and 6.4-7.6 ppm (aromatic protons); M⁺ at m/z 314.

Similarly, other compounds (IVb to IVj) were prepared by the condensation of fluorine containing indole-2,3-dione with appropriate aniline. The purification was achieved by crystallization and characterised by elemental analysis, ir and nmr spectra. IR $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{cm}^{-1}}$: 1640-1750 (>C=O), 3280-3320 (NH); pmr (CDCl₃) δ : 3.8-4.3 (CH₂), 7.8-11.0 (NH), 6.4-7.6 ppm (aromatic proton); M⁺ at m/z 332 (IVb and IVc).

Antifertility activity : The compounds IVb, IVc, IVg and IVi were tested for anti-implantation activity by the reported procedure¹⁴. Only compound IVg is active at the dose of 30 mg/kg in rats. Further screening of this compound is in progress.

* Part II : Joshi *et al*, *Indian J. Chem.*, (1983) in press.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL, CHARACTERISTIC AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS IVa TO IVj

Compound No.	X	Y	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formulas	% Nitrogen*	
						Found/(Calcd.)	
IVa	5-F	H	265	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ FN ₂ O ₂ S	9.18	(8.91)
IVb	5-F	4-F	180	90	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ F ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.19	(8.43)
IVc	5-F	3-F	214	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ F ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.17	(8.43)
IVd	5-F	3-CF ₃	222	50	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ F ₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	7.07	(7.33)
IVe	5-F	2,3,5,6-tetra F	117	40	C ₁₆ H ₇ F ₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.28	(7.91)
IVf	6-F	H	245	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ FN ₂ O ₂ S	9.00	(8.91)
IVg	6-F	4-F	270	75	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ F ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.26	(8.43)
IVh	6-F	3-F	220	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ F ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.31	(8.43)
IVi	6-F	3-CF ₃	225	85	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ F ₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	7.27	(7.33)
IVj	4-CF ₃	4-F	282	85	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ F ₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	7.30	(7.33)

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and S analyses.

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